

Herbicide-azolla integration for weed control in transplanted IR60 rice

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In a field experiment at TNAU in rabi 1987, we studied the weed-suppressing ability of azolla alone and with herbicides. We used a randomized complete block design with three replications.

The herbicide treatments (see table) were imposed 3 d after transplanting (DT) and azolla was inoculated 9 DT and incorporated at 30 DT (except in treatment 8). Weed dry matter (DM) was recorded at 60 DT.

The weed flora included *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Ammannia baccifera*, and *Eclipta alba*.

Hand weeding twice (HWT) + azolla (treatment 6), anilofos + 2,4-D EE + azolla (treatment 2), and thiobencarb +

Effect of weed control treatments on weed dry matter (DM) and relative dry weight, and grain yield of rice. ^a TNAU, 1987 dry season.

Treatment	Weed DM at 60 DT (g/0.5 m ²)	Weed efficiency (%)	Relative dry weight (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)
			Echinochloa	Marsilea	
1 Anilofos 0.30 kg/ha + 2,4-D EE at 0.51 kg/ha	6.5 cd	73.47	46.15	23.08	5.0 b
2 T1 + azolla DC at 2 t/ha	3.0 ab	87.76	60.00	16.67	5.2 b
3 Thiobencarb 1.0 kg/ha + 2,4-D EE at 0.51 kg/ha	7.5 d	69.39	40.00	26.68	4.9 bc
4 T3 + azolla DC at 2 t/ha	3.8 ab	84.49	68.40	10.53	5.1 b
5 Two hand weedings	4.8 bc	80.41	50.00	20.83	5.7 a
6 T5 + azolla DC at 2 t/ha	1.5 a	93.88	53.30	13.33	5.8 a
7 Unweeded check	24.5 f	—	60.95	12.24	4.1 d
8 T7 + azolla DC at 2 t/ha	15.6 e	36.33	50.64	22.44	4.6 c

^a In a column any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level. DC = dual culture.

2,4-D EE + azolla (treatment 4) effectively reduced weed DM at 60 DT (see table). Azolla effectively suppressed *Marsilea* but not *Echinochloa*.

HWT + azolla recorded the highest weed control efficiency of 93.88% at 60 DT, followed by anilofos + 2,4-D EE + azolla with 87.76%. Weed control efficiency at 60 DT was strongly

correlated with yield $r = +0.89^{**}$.

Two hand weedings alone or in combination with azolla as dual culture recorded higher yields. Herbicide-treated plots either singly or in combination with azolla recorded lower yields, but these were significantly higher than that of the unweeded check alone or with azolla. □

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of N forms on leaf nitrate reductase activity, yield, and protein content of rice

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Using 4 replications, we studied the relationship of leaf nitrate reductase activity (NRA) at crop growth stages to yield and protein content of rough rice as affected by N forms during 1987 WS at Agricultural College, Bapatla.

MTU5249 (Vajram) was grown in glazed pots (6 kg soil/pot) under flooded conditions. The seedlings (3 wk) were transplanted at 2 seedlings/pot and fertilized separately with potassium nitrate, urea, and ammonium sulfate

(120 kg N/ha) with a basal dose of superphosphate (40 kg P/ha) and muriate of potash (40 kg K/ha). Control was no N. N was supplied in 3 split doses-at transplanting, 25 d after transplanting (DT), and 50 DT. Experimental soil was heavy-textured clay loam with pH 7.0, 0.45% organic C, and 94-12-700 kg available NPK/ha.

Leaf NRA was assayed in the uppermost leaf or flag leaf at maximum tillering > panicle initiation > flowering stages. It was in the order maximum tillering > panicle initiation > flowering (see table). Potassium nitrate treatment recorded highest NRA, followed by urea and ammonium sulfate. Neither grain yields nor protein contents differed significantly among N forms. However, N fertilizer improved grain yield and protein content compared to the control. □

Leaf NRA, grain yield, and protein content of MTU5249 rice as affected by different forms of fertilizer N. Bapatla, India, 1987 WS.

Treatment	Leaf NRA (nmol NO ₂ ⁻ formed/g per h)			Grain yield (g/pot)	Grain protein (%)
	Maximum tillering	Panicle initiation	Flowering		
Control	150	110	90	3.10	7.61
Potassium nitrate	460	410	380	9.85	9.45
Urea	420	385	360	10.45	8.62
Ammonium sulfate	405	360	345	9.42	8.55
LSD (0.05)	38	25	31	1.15	0.92